

THE PROCESS OF DEVELOPING THE CREATIVE ABILITIES OF FUTURE ENGINEERS

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Abstract. *In this article, the ability of students to have creativity is its personal qualities, the quality of natural and social activities, and directs to effective organization. The creative ability of students studying in the higher education system is shown in the environment for developing new ideas, not thinking in a single mold, originality, initiative skills, different from the traditional approach to the organization of educational and upbringing processes.*

Keywords: *creativity, traditional, creative ability, success.*

The process of developing the creative abilities of future engineers is organized in the following stages. Under the guidance of a professor-teacher, the organization of students' creativity, extremely strongly stimulating the acquisition and strengthening of knowledge, the development of creative activity in the process of developing creativity, is one of the most effective directions in the educational process. This, to a certain extent, serves to fulfill the tasks noted in the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PD-5847 dated October 8, 2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", Resolutions PR-3775 dated June 5, 2018 "On additional measures to improve the quality of education in higher education institutions and ensure their active participation in large-scale reforms implemented in the country", PR-4022 dated November 21, 2018 "On measures to further modernize the digital infrastructure", PR-4884 dated November 6, 2020 "On additional measures to further improve the education system" and other regulatory legal acts.

According to A.G. Mikhaylova, the introduction of a creative approach is manifested in the development of creative thinking together with practice. The family plays a big role in the development of the student's creative ability. At the same time, parents are able to develop or destroy a person's creative abilities. The development of creative thinking skills of gifted students depends on good relations between their parents and teachers. She emphasizes that the role of the father is of great importance in the development of students' creative abilities [2].

According to G.N.Ibragimova's opinion, she states in her research that "required the development of the content of students' creativity development according to the possibilities, directions, determination of motivation, creativity qualities, conditions and stages of development of students' creative abilities. The process of developing creativity in students allows the creation of heuristic developments based on interactive methods and technologies in the higher education system due to the fact that it depends on the effective organization of a person-oriented educational process by professors and teachers." [4].

The simplest example of this approach is to present works of art and literature as products of the artist's fantasy, and then conclude that creativity is a form of neurotic fantasy. It can be seen from this hypothesis that it cannot explain why all dreams are not creative. If we emphasize that any person is a creator in some field of knowledge, it is self-evident that if all the obstacles that

arise in the process of creation are eliminated, it is important to be able to achieve real results in the activity.

Figure 1.

From the presented concepts on the development of creativity, we believe that the development of creativity in overcoming obstacles will bring out the creative abilities of every student studying in higher education institutions.

In our opinion, creativity develops most successfully in an environment characterized by the absence of criticism, intrusive assessment and stress, and students perform creative tasks and intellectual tasks much better. This situation is manifested in the first period of development of students' creativity.

Valuable conclusions are given that the manifestation of the process of developing the creative ability of future engineers can be determined by the following criteria:

- identifying the problem;
- the ability to synthesize, feel similarities and understand differences;
- thinking differently;
- fluency of thinking.

In our research, the creative activities of high-intelligent students were studied, equating them with the creative activities of specialists and teachers, and their development as a creative and active person with high potential.

The main attention in the development of the research ability of students studying at a higher educational institution can be formulated as follows.

- theoretical justification of the essence of the concept of "creative ability", which implies the existence of creative and intellectual initiative; the ability to create new original ideas in solving problematic issues; an adequate way out of the problematic situation that arose during the educational process; the ability to adapt to changes and non-standard situations that occur in the educational process.

- pedagogical conditions for the development of students' creativity during the educational process, including a favorable climate in the student community for the development of the spirit of creativity; designing problem situations that allow the development of arbitrary attention, memory, logical thinking during the educational process; organization of subject-mental activity of students using the author's teaching technology; involving students in research activities; organization of a system of independent work on the development of students' creativity.

- author's teaching technology, created on the basis of a special model, is aimed at arousing students' interest in academic subjects; is manifested in improving the quality of students' knowledge; activation of educational work of students; the involvement of students in research activities.

Summarizing all of the above, it should be noted that various aspects of the problem of creativity are actively studied by foreign and domestic experts, and the results of these studies are widely used in the development of various programs for identifying and developing creative potential..

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